

ICT IN TEACHING BLIND AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Karimova Nazokat Zoirjon qizi¹

Sharipova Yoqut Quدراتillayevna²

¹MA student, UZSWLU, Tashkent

nazokatjaju91@gmail.com

Under the supervision

²Senior teacher, UZSWLU, Tashkent

yakutkhan82@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6592697>

Abstract: The right to education belongs to all children, including children with disabilities, regardless of the causes of disability. Ensuring equal rights and equal opportunities for a child with disabilities is priority direction in the field of modern education. This article discusses the importance modern technology in Teaching languages to Blind and Visually Impaired (below BVI) learners.

Key words: BVI learners, modern technologies, learning languages, teaching languages, Braille, Braille display.

According to the World Health Organization, there are 246 million visually impaired people worldwide and about 39 million blind people. According to some data, the number of recorded blind and visually impaired people in Uzbekistan is around 66 thousand people, of which 20 thousand are absolutely blind (USAID, 2020). Of this number, 22% are young people of working age. Is it worth talking about the need to educate the blind, when almost one in five blind people can get a job with some help and training? However, accurate statistics are almost impossible to find and various experts claim that there are actually many more blind people [1].

Teaching English to visually impaired people is an even more difficult task, but knowledge of the language expands the educational opportunities of such people, allowing them to become part of the global educational environment and feel socially adapted in society. In addition, visually impaired specialists with knowledge of a foreign language are not numerous in Uzbekistan.

The specificity of teaching people with visual impairments is due to the limited access to information. For their training, a special system of measures and specific didactic materials are needed. It is quite obvious that it is necessary to search for new approaches to create rational methods for teaching, correcting and rehabilitating visually impaired people. In this study, the authors propose a completely new approach to teaching blind people any didactic disciplines taught on the example of a foreign language. This new methodology may also be attractive because it is generally available to all people with visual impairments,

regardless of nationality and the language spoken by students. To date, there are quite a few computer hardware and software typhlotechnical tools that provide people with visual impairments with the opportunity to independently use a regular personal computer. These are programs for non-visual or screen access to information (screen reader), a Braille display, a Braille keyboard, a Braille printer, voice speech synthesizers, etc. According to the functions performed and the process of work, computer typhlotechnical means are divided into means of relief-dot and sound output or input of computer information [2].

The key tool for a blind or visually impaired user is a program for non-visual or screen access to information (screenreader). The program reads information from the computer screen and, using the built-in speech synthesizer, displays visual text on the tool, sound or relief-dot output [2]. Quite a few screen reader programs have been developed, but Non Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) and Jawsfor Windows have become popular and most widely used in Uzbekistan.

The free program NVDA (Non Visual Desktop Access), translated as "non-visual access to the desktop", interacts with the Windows operating system, supports Mozilla Firefox and Google Chrome web browsers, Microsoft Word, Excel office programs and others.

The built-in speech synthesizer reproduces speech in more than 50 languages [3]. One of the advantages of the NVDA program is its portability and the fact that it almost does not change the appearance of the operating system [4]. Another popular screen reader is Jawsfor Windows. Quite easy to use, it provides work with popular computer applications, displays information using a voice speech synthesizer and a tactile Braille display [5].

Audio output means include software speech synthesizers that convert text information into speech. Sound output hardware today, with the development of operating systems, has been almost completely replaced. The use of a computer without the use of special hardware made the computer accessible to blind users.

There are many software speech synthesizers, for example, eSpeak, RHVoice and others. Important parameters that determine consumer properties are speech quality, quick response to a control action and playback speed. To characterize the quality of speech, such concepts as "naturalness of sound", "phonetic intelligibility", "comfort of perception" and "accustoming time" are usually used [6]. The question of which synthesizer is better cannot be answered unambiguously, everyone chooses individually, corresponding to him in terms of parameters or characteristics. Today, many operating systems, such as Windows, have a built-in speech synthesizer.

Based on the functionality of the above typhlotechnical means, it can be concluded that people with vision problems, having a personal computer with an installed screen reader program or a speech synthesizer built into the operating system and a regular keyboard can use it freely. "But one should not think that computer methods of accessing information are replacing traditional Braille. So far, nothing more convenient and versatile than the relief-dot writing system for the blind has been invented. Far from any information can be perceived by ear, for example, proofs of theorems are much easier to digest when reading. In these situations, there are no alternatives to braille" [7].

And also "the Braille display is indispensable when learning foreign languages, since foreign-language synthesizers, although they can contribute to the development of perception of foreign speech, practically do not give an idea of the spelling of words. In addition, the perception of a foreign text by ear is much more difficult than reading" [2, p. 54].

However, the results of this and other studies show that not all tiphlo-technical equipment is available for blind and visually impaired children for a number of reasons, among which we can highlight the high cost and low level of logistics: "As our survey data showed, the effective work of teachers and educators in The field of social rehabilitation of visually impaired children is largely hampered by the following factors: insufficient provision of educational and methodological literature and individual tiphlo-devices - 43%, low level of logistics - 31% ... "[8, p. 217].

The search for new ways and solutions that can serve as alternatives to expensive and less accessible programs and devices for people with visual impairments, especially those who are completely blind, is an urgent task in typhlopedagogy.

ICT is becoming an indispensable assistant in increasing interest students to studied problems and develops visual-figurative thinking, because, without being in the country of the language being studied, to master the communicative competence in English is a very difficult matter. With students we, teachers, are forced to artificially create a communication environment that, to unfortunately ends co call with lesson English language. And the use of information computer technologies gives fundamentally new opportunities for raise efficiency educational process. This is an expansion of access to information in the usual verbal and other forms, increasing the expressive possibilities of providing information, the combination of its rational and emotional aspects, the inclusion of game elements, the ability to use models, a wide range of methodological tools, replication and improvement teaching materials and simplification of their

transmission over a distance, new opportunities in the concentration of information, individualization educational process and its variability, new opportunities in organization of interdisciplinary connections, the release of the teacher from the routine labor and focusing its attention on creative or extraordinary moments promotion interest to obtaining knowledge.

The ICT breakthrough currently taking place is forcing reconsider the organization of information support cognitive activity. Thus, ICT allows us to consider opportunities use information technologies in educational activities:

1. to search for literature, on the World Wide Web using browsers type Internet explorer, Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome and etc., various search systems (Yandex, Rambler, Mai, google, Yahoo and etc.) and work with her (abstracting, taking notes, annotating, quoting and etc.);
2. for working with texts using the package of basic applied programs Microsoft office: Microsoft Word allows create and edit texts with graphic design; Microsoft PowerPoint allows create presentation slides for more colorful demonstration of the material; Microsoft Excel Run computing, analyze and visualize data and work co lists in tables and on web pages; Microsoft Office Publisher allows create and change booklets, brochures and etc.
3. for automatic translation texts with help programs-translators (Promt) and electronic dictionaries (AbbyLingvo);
4. for storage and accumulation information (CD-, DVDs, USB flash-drives and portable HDD);
5. for communication (VK, e-mail, ICQ, skype, mail agent, Viber and etc.);
6. for processing and playback charts and sound (turntables, Microsoft media player, winamp, win-dvd, POT player, etc., programs for viewing and editing images ACDSee, Adobe photoshop, Corel Draw, programs for creation schemes, drawings and charts Visio) and others;

Listed facilities ICT create favorable opportunities in English lessons also for organizing independent work of students. They help you use computer technologies both for studying individual topics and for self-control received knowledge and self-correction.

Modern programs require the student concentration attention concentration, voltage various species memory. Not everyone schoolboy able work in such mode. Psychological peculiarities character, type perception child become reason for failure. At the same time, modern requirements for the level education do not allow to reduce the amount of information needed student for assimilation themes lesson.

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